

Performance-Optimized Double-Tail Dynamic Comparator for High-Speed and Low-Power Operation in 90 nm CMOS

S. Rama Rao, Poluri Chandra Akhila, Mekala Venkata Sai Vinay, Shaik Nagurvali, Shaik Shameem

Department of Electronics and Communications Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Mothadaka, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India.

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KEYWORDS

Dynamic comparator, low power, High speed.

ABSTRACT

As a key building block, the comparator plays an important role in various types of analog-to-digital converters (ADCs). Especially, in high-speed high-resolution SAR ADCs, the ADC sampling rate and accuracy are limited by the comparator speed, kickback noise, input referred noise, and offset. Under this circumstance, it is important to design a high-performance comparator. High-speed and low-power comparators are critical building blocks in modern analog-to-digital converters and mixed-signal systems. This paper presents an efficient design of a double-tail dynamic comparator optimized for high-speed and low-power applications in 180 nm CMOS technology. The proposed comparator architecture employs a double-tail structure that allows operation at low supply voltages while achieving reduced power consumption and improved speed. By separating the input and latch stages, the design minimizes static power dissipation and mitigates kickback noise, thereby enhancing input-referred offset performance. Transistor-level optimization and careful sizing further improve the regeneration speed and reduce decision delay. Post-layout simulations conducted in 90 nm technology demonstrate that the proposed comparator achieves high-speed operation with significantly lower power consumption compared to conventional dynamic comparators, making it well suited for high-resolution and high-speed ADC applications

I. INTRODUCTION

A comparator is an essential component in the construction of analogue to digital converter (ADCs), which find application in several fields including radar,

optical communications, microwave and wide band radio receivers, data acquisition systems, and radar. Comparators are the main component of the flash ADC architecture [1]. A comparator compares an input signal

(V_{in}) to a reference signal (V_{ref}) and produces an output signal that is either high or may be low

which is based on the differential signal of input. Static comparators are widely employed in applications for portable electronic devices in the modern world. Low power design, volt scaling, as well as other dynamical power-saving measures can reduce the total power use of CMOS circuits.

Numerous design topologies have been created to increase comparators speed. A CMOS current comparator has good accuracy and speed, but it has significant static power dissipation when the device is off. In order to lower the static power dissipation with larger transistor sizes, a CMOS dynamic voltage comparator has been developed.

Consequently, reduced speed and larger chip size were exchanged for a lower offset voltage. Because they have less delay and don't produce static power dissipation, dynamic comparators are recommended in ADCs over CMOS static comparators. Using various approaches and methodologies, Dynamic comparators are designed for applications that require little power. The changing dynamic comparator's speed as well as precision will be improved by reducing the possibility of meta stability. A 1-stage dynamic comparator was came into existence to increase speed while reducing power use. Nevertheless, kick-back noise was produced by parasitic capacitances between the single-stage dynamic comparator's input and output nodes [4]. The dual tail dynamic comparator is designed to reduce kickback noise while increasing speed. This offers a more optimal balance between power and speed. In addition, by using two cross couple transistors made from PMOS in the preamplifier stage, the typical DTDC is modified to provide reduced-power, fast operation at limited supply voltages. A low-power dynamic comparator was built by connecting two additional inverters between the input and also output stages of a traditional DTDC. As a result, the offset voltage and latch stage gain were both raised. To lower the offset voltage, a dynamic comparator is equipped with a basic latch which operates according to a specified pattern of clocking [5]. Yet this architecture restricts the fastness of comparator. To boost the speed latch, a redesigned DTDC with having cross-coupled loads MC1 and MC2 for the stage amplification was designed. However, this led to a rise in the amount of power used. While developing less-power comparators, the

preamplifier's consumption of power is critical. The goal of a dynamic comparator is to lower the power consumed of the pre-amplifier stage with preserving its offset voltage.

However, inadequate supply voltage renders developing a fast speed comparator far more challenging. As a result, there is a compromise between energy use and efficiency of speed [2]. A new double tail dynamic comparator is suggested after taking the aforementioned drawbacks into account. The suggested design's primary goal is to reduce power usage and delay. The suggested approach speeds up a latch stage by using switching techniques. Pre-amplifier and latch stage are its two stages. The comparator's latency is improved by the latch stage and its gain is improved by the pre-amplifier stage. To lower the comparator's overdrive voltage, 2 PMOS switching transistors are added to the 1st stage of latch.

Consequently, there is a decrease in both power usage and latency. Additionally, when an input differential transistor was sized appropriately, the input offset voltage likewise reduced. By using a clock frequency of 1 GHz and a supply voltage of 0.8 V, the design and implementation of this suggested one is completed in 90 nm CMOS cadence virtuoso technology. Comparing the suggested double tail dynamic comparator to the previous studies, the simulation results validate a significant reduction in both power consumption and delay time.

2. Literature Survey

A 1.2-V Dynamic Bias Latch-Type Comparator in 65-nm CMOS With 0.4-mV Input Noise by H. S. Bindra, C. E. Lokin, D. Schinkel, A.-J. Annema, and B. Nauta:

A latch-type comparator with a dynamic bias pre-amplifier is implemented in a 65-nm CMOS process. The dynamic bias with a tail capacitor is simple to implement and ensures that the pre-amplifier output nodes are only partially discharged to reduce the energy consumption. The comparator is analyzed and compared to its prior art in terms of energy consumption and input referred noise voltage. First-order equations are presented that show how to optimize the pre-amplifier for low noise and high gain. Both the dynamic bias comparator and the prior art are implemented on the same die and measurements show that the dynamic bias can reduce the average energy

consumption by about a factor 2.5 for the same input-equivalent noise at an input common-mode level of half the supply voltage.

An 8-bit 150-MHz CMOS A/D converter by Y. T. Wang *et al.*:

This paper describes an 8-bit 5-stage pipelined and interleaved analog-to-digital converter that performs analog processing only by means of open-loop circuits such as differential pairs and source followers to achieve a high conversion rate. The concept of sliding interpolation is proposed to obviate the need for a large number of comparators or interstage digital-to-analog converters and residue amplifiers. The pipelining scheme incorporates distributed sampling between the stages so as to relax the linearity-speed tradeoffs in the sample-and-hold circuits. A clock edge reassignment technique is also introduced that suppresses timing mismatches in interleaved systems, and a punctured interpolation method is proposed that reduces the integral nonlinearity error with negligible speed or power penalty. Fabricated in a 0.6- μm CMOS technology, the converter achieves differential and integral nonlinearities of 0.62 and 1.24 LSB, respectively, and a signal-to-(noise+distortion) ratio of 43.7 dB at a sampling rate of 150 MHz. The circuit draws 395 mW from a 3.3-V supply and occupies an area of 1.2/spl times/1.5 mm/sup 2/.

Analysis and Design of a Low-Voltage Low-Power Double-Tail Comparator by S. Babayan-Mashhadi and R. Lotfi:

The need for ultra low-power, area efficient, and high speed analog-to-digital converters is pushing toward the use of dynamic regenerative comparators to maximize speed and power efficiency. In this paper, an analysis on the delay of the dynamic comparators will be presented and analytical expressions are derived. From the analytical expressions, designers can obtain an intuition about the main contributors to the comparator delay and fully explore the tradeoffs in dynamic comparator design. Based on the presented analysis, a new dynamic comparator is proposed, where the circuit of a conventional double-tail comparator is modified for low-power and fast operation even in small supply voltages. Without complicating the design and by adding few transistors, the positive feedback during the regeneration is strengthened, which results in remarkably reduced delay time. Post-layout simulation

results in a 0.18- μm CMOS technology confirm the analysis results. It is shown that in the proposed dynamic comparator both the power consumption and delay time are significantly reduced. The maximum clock frequency of the proposed comparator can be increased to 2.5 and 1.1 GHz at supply voltages of 1.2 and 0.6 V, while consuming 1.4 mW and 153 μW , respectively. The standard deviation of the input-referred offset is 7.8 mV at 1.2 V supply.

A Low-Power High-Speed Comparator for Precise Applications by A. Khorami and M. Sharifkhani:

A low-power comparator is presented. pMOS transistors are used at the input of the preamplifier of the comparator as well as the latch stage. Both stages are controlled by a special local clock generator. At the evaluation phase, the latch is activated with a delay to achieve enough preamplification gain and avoid excess power consumption. Meanwhile, small cross-coupled transistors increase the preamplifier gain and decrease the input common mode of the latch to strongly turn on the pMOS transistors (at the latch input) and reduce the delay. Unlike the conventional comparator, the proposed structure let us set the optimum delay for preamplification and avoid excess power consumption. The speed and the power benefits of the comparator were verified using solid analytical derivations, process-VDD-temperature corners, and Monte Carlo simulations along with silicon measurements in 0.18 μm . The tests confirm that the proposed circuit reduces the power consumption by 50% and provides 30% better comparison speed at the same offset and almost the same noise budgets. Moreover, the comparator provides a rail-to-rail input V_{cm} range in $f_{\text{clk}}=500\text{MHz}$.

II. A LOW-POWER HIGH-PRECISION COMPARATOR WITH TIME-DOMAIN BULK-TUNED OFFSET CANCELLATION BY J. LU AND J. HOLLEMAN:

A novel time-domain bulk-tuned offset cancellation technique is applied to a low-power high-precision dynamic comparator to reduce its input-referred offset with minimal additional power consumption and delay. The design has been fabricated in a commercially available 0.5- μm process. Measurement results of 10 circuits show a reduction of offset standard deviation from 5.415 mV to 50.57 μV , improved by a factor of 107.1. The offset cancellation scheme does not introduce observable offset or noise, and can achieve fast and robust convergence with a wide range of common mode

input. Operating at a supply of 5 V and clock frequency of 200 kHz, the comparator together with the OC circuitry consumes 4.65 μW of power, or 23 pJ of energy per comparison.

3. Existing Method

There are two types of comparators namely, Open-loop comparators and Regenerative or latch comparators. Open loop comparators are basically Op-amps without a feed-back whereas, regenerative comparators use positive feed-back mechanism to compare two signals. Many applications uses Op-amp as an open-loop voltage comparator, but this method is generally not accurate and leads to slow performance. Hence the dynamic latch comparators used. It consists of an input pre-amplifier stage. At the reset phase ($\text{Clk}=0$) the output is pre-charged to logic "1". The output is evaluated at the regeneration phase ($\text{Clk}=1$).

There are three phases of operation, namely the reset phase, the amplification phase, and the regeneration phase. In the reset phase ($\text{CLK} = 0$), the comparator is reset. In the amplification phase ($\text{CLK} = 1$), the input signal $V_{IP}-V_{IN}$ is amplified and sent to the latch stage. In the regeneration phase, OUTP and OUTN regenerate to V_{DD} or GND . As mentioned before, such a structure has the limitation of pMOS input pair in the latch stage.

Fig1: Circuit diagram of Conventional Double-tail Dynamic latch comparator

The Double-tail dynamic latch comparator is a comparator which has better performance at low voltage application. The Double-tail dynamic latch comparator has two discrete stages for input and for regenerative

latch. Due to the separate stages, the comparator operates at a low voltage. Hence have stable offset voltage and increased speed [5]. Due to the presence of two tails one at the input stage and one at latch stage, the current is driven by two separate transistors. This is an advantage over the single tail comparators, in which the current is driven by single tail and it requires high power. The circuit diagram of conventional Double-tail dynamic latch comparator is shown in Figure 1. During the positive edge of the clock the tail transistors $M1$ and $M12$ are ON. $M4$ and $M5$ are OFF. The output nodes are reset. During the negative edge of the clock the tail transistors $M1$ and $M12$ are OFF. Transistors $M4$ and $M5$ are ON. The nodes D_{i+} and D_{i-} are charged to input voltages. Due to the arrangement of cross coupling inverters at latch stage a positive feed-back is produced and the output is evaluated.

4. Proposed Method

In order to reduce the kickback noise and further improve the speed, this brief proposes a comparator, Figure 2 shows the modified Double-tail dynamic latch comparator circuit diagram. The size of tail transistor M_{tail1} is measured to have a low tail current through a differential input pair to achieve a longer integration time and a better g_m / I_D ratio for a large gain (less offset). The size of tail transistor M_{tail2} is selected to have large tail current at the output stage for faster regeneration time

Fig2: Circuit diagram of Double-tail Dynamic latch comparator

The two inverters are connected in cross-coupling format and provide a positive feedback and good shielding between input stage and output stage to reduce kick-back noise. [3]. Diode connected transistors $M3$ and $M4$ were inserted between the input transistors.

This reduces the output swing from V_{dd} to 0 to $(V_{dd} - V_{ds})$ to 0. Hence reduces the dynamic power dissipation. During the positive edge of the clock the tail transistors M_{tail1} and M_{tail2} are ON. Transistor M_5 is OFF. The output nodes are reset to V_{ss} . During the negative edge of the clock, tail transistors are OFF.

Transistor M_5 is ON. The nodes D_i+ and D_i- are charged to input voltages. The cross coupled inverter pair provides positive feed-back and the output is evaluated. This phase is called regeneration phase. The power is dissipated only in regeneration phase of the comparator which reduces the total power consumption

The schematic of modified Double-tail latch comparator is shown in Figure 3. The input tail transistor M_1 is sized to have a small current driving capability. The tail transistor M_{13} at the latch stage is sized to have large current driving capability. The cross coupled inverter reduces offset voltage at the output.

In a double-tail dynamic comparator, the **preamplification stage** is responsible for initially amplifying the small differential input voltage before it is applied to the regenerative latch. This stage typically consists of a differential input pair controlled by the first tail transistor and operates only during the evaluation phase of the clock. When the clock is low, the tail transistor is off and the output nodes are precharged, resulting in zero static power consumption. During evaluation, the tail transistor turns on, allowing the differential input pair to convert the input voltage difference into a current difference, which produces a small voltage difference at the preamplifier output nodes.

This extra preamplifier acts as an inverter, and makes the latch stage able to use nMOS input pair

M_{11-12} instead of pMOS input pair, which leads to increased speed. The extra preamplifier also provides voltage gain, thus improving the regeneration speed and suppressing the input referred offset and noise.

Fig3: Preamplifiers

This preamplification improves the overall performance of the comparator by reducing input-referred offset, minimizing kickback noise, and enabling faster and more reliable decisions in scaled technologies such as 90 nm CMOS. By separating the amplification and latching actions, the double-tail architecture allows better operation at low supply voltages while maintaining high speed and low power consumption. Proper sizing of the input transistors, tail current, and load devices ensures a balanced trade-off between gain, speed, and power efficiency.

By contrast, the proposed modified version of three-stage comparator can solve these issues. It has the fastest speed and the smallest kickback noise compared to other comparators.

5. Results and Discussion

The results presented in this project demonstrate the design, simulation, and performance evaluation of the double-tail comparator (VLSI circuit). These results are obtained using circuit design and simulation tools (such as Tanner EDA), which validate the functionality of the comparator.

Fig 5: Schematic Diagram of Double Tail Comparator

This figure illustrates the complete transistor-level schematic of the double-tail comparator used in the design. It consists of a differential input stage, tail current transistors, and a regenerative latch stage formed by cross-coupled inverters. The comparator operates by comparing two input voltages and producing a digital output based on their difference. The double-tail structure helps in reducing power consumption while improving speed. The schematic confirms that all components are properly connected and the circuit is correctly designed for high-speed and low-power applications

Fig 6: Simulation Setup / Netlist Window

This figure shows the simulation setup, including the netlist and configuration parameters used for analyzing the circuit. It contains details of voltage sources, transistor models, node connections, and simulation commands such as transient analysis. The inputs and power supply values are clearly defined, ensuring proper biasing of the circuit. This setup is essential for accurately simulating the behavior of the comparator and verifying its performance under specified conditions.

Fig 7: Transient Response / Output Waveforms

This figure presents the transient analysis results in the form of waveforms. It displays the input voltages, clock signal, and output responses of the comparator over time. The waveforms show how the comparator responds during different phases of operation. When one input voltage exceeds the other, the output switches accordingly, demonstrating correct comparator functionality. The outputs exhibit fast transitions and clear logic levels, indicating high-speed operation and effective decision-making capability of the circuit.

Fig 8: Performance Summary (Power and Timing Analysis)

This figure provides a summary of the simulation results, including key performance parameters such as power consumption, timing characteristics, and analysis statistics. It reflects how efficiently the circuit operates under the given conditions. The results indicate that the comparator achieves low power consumption along with fast response time, making it suitable for VLSI applications. This summary validates the effectiveness and reliability of the proposed design.

6. Conclusion

The different types of Dynamic latch comparators are simulated using 180 nm CMOS Technology in tanner eda environment. The modified Double-tail dynamic latch comparator is free from glitches at the intermediate nodes. The power consumed by the different types of comparators are tabulated. The modified Double-tail Dynamic latch comparator consumes 296.17 pW which is lower compared to power dissipated by other types of comparators. Though it has more number of transistors in the design, the delay is reduced compared to other comparators. Comparator and its modified version, which have the advantages of fast speed, low kickback noise, and low input referred offset and noise. These comparators are well suited for high-speed high-resolution SAR ADCs. Finally, measured results validate the effectiveness of these comparators

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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